

THE EFFECT OF INTRINSIC MOTIVATION ON EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION DURING THE DIGITAL AGE WITH INCENTIVES AS INTERVENING VARIABLES (CASE STUDY ON EMPLOYEES OF THE ONE STOP INTEGRATED LICENSING AND INVESTMENT SERVICE IN MEDAN CITY)

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Abstract

This study aims to find out how the Influence of Intrinsic Motivation on Employee Satisfaction During the Digital Age With Incentives As Intervening Variables (Case Study on Employees of the One-Stop Integrated Investment and Licensing Service in Medan). The research method used is the method of qualitative data and quantitative data. While the data used are primary and secondary data. The data analysis method in this study used simple linear regression analysis and path analysis. As for the results of this study, the first hypothesis was rejected, meaning that the variable Motivation Intrinsic (X) has no positive and significant effect on Employee Satisfaction (Z), the second hypothesis is accepted, meaning that Intrinsic Motivation (X) significant effect on Employee Satisfaction (Y), the third hypothesis is rejected, meaning that the Incentive (Z) no effect positive and significant on Employee Satisfaction (Y), path analysis shows the direct effect of variable X on variable Y of 0.545. While the indirect effect through the Z variable is $0.192 \times 0.008 = 0.0153$ from the calculation results obtained, it shows that the indirect effect through the Z variable is smaller than the direct effect on the Y variable.

Keywords: Intrinsic Motivation, Incentives and Employee Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the development of human resources in Indonesia has begun to grow rapidly along with the increasing number of people in Indonesia. The increasingly fierce business competition today forces organizations to empower and optimize all their limited resources so that companies must manage them effectively and efficiently. The number of large and small institutions that have fallen cannot be separated from the bleak history of managing human resources (HR) that are owned in a bad way, despite having abundant natural resources. Regardless of the type of natural resources owned by an organization, HR still occupies the most strategic and very important position among other resources.

Employees are a very valuable agency asset and must be managed properly by the agency in order to make an optimal contribution. This shows that human resources are the main key that

must be considered with all their needs. As the main key, human resources will determine the success of implementing agency activities. Therefore, the success or failure of an organization or institution will be determined by the human factor or its employees in achieving its goals. The company management in increasing employee satisfaction must always pay attention to the factors that encourage employees to work productively, one of which is increasing employee motivation. According to Robbins (2010: 301) "Employee satisfaction is the general attitude of an individual towards his work, which shows the difference between the number of awards received by workers and the amount they believe they will get what they need. The greater the employee's needs are met, the more satisfied the employee will be. And vice versa, the fewer employee needs are not met, the employee will feel dissatisfied. Employees who get employee satisfaction will carry out their work better, employees who do not get employee satisfaction will never reach psychological maturity which will cause frustration. Employees like this will often daydream, low morale, get bored and tired quickly, emotionally unstable, often absent and doing activities that have nothing to do with the work they have to do.

Employee satisfaction is a general attitude that is more colored by feelings towards the work situation and environment and is a reflection of an employee's satisfaction with conditions related to the implementation of work. Employee dissatisfaction can occur if the work done is not in accordance with what is obtained from the agency. The dissatisfaction of these employees causes things that are not desirable and can be detrimental to the agency concerned. For example; there are strikes, employee absenteeism increases, employee performance decreases, and so on. So, leaders should understand what employees need, know what desires make employees satisfied, and all the consequences, including what and how much bonus they will receive if their work targets or goals are achieved. So that employees will be motivated and not do things that are not appropriate to be done, employee satisfaction can occur and can be seen from a pleasant or unpleasant emotional state where employees view their work. Employee satisfaction reflects a person's feelings towards his job. This can be seen in the positive attitude of employees towards work and everything that is faced in the work environment.

The success of the agency in achieving its goals cannot be separated from the role of employees. Employees are not only objects in achieving agency goals, but also become subjects or actors. They can be planners, implementers and controllers who always play an active role in realizing agency goals, and have thoughts, feelings and desires that can influence their attitudes towards work. To improve the quality and quantity of employee performance, it can be done in many ways such as improving the quality of providing incentives, training, education, providing motivation, and creating a conducive work environment.

Developments in the increasingly rapid digital era demand that every agencies to follow the changes that occur, especially in processing human resources within the agency. Of course, human resources are very plays an important role in realizing the goals and vision and mission of the agency. Because employees in the agency are one of the factors that play an important role in every agency. Both in terms of planning, organizing, implementing, controlling so that agency goals can be achieved properly and efficiently.

According to Hasibuan Melayu SP (2017:22) states "Incentives are additional remuneration given to certain employees whose achievements are above standard achievements. This incentive wage is a tool used by supporters of the fair principle in providing compensation." According to Mangkunegara (2011) states "Incentives are a form of money given by organizational leaders to employees so that they work with high motivation and achievement in achieving organizational goals as an acknowledgment of work performance and employee contributions to the organization."

Incentives obtained by employees are divided into 2 types, namely material incentives and non-material incentives. Material incentives can be interpreted as an incentive given to employees in the form of money or goods. Then non-material incentives can be interpreted as an incentive in the form of awards, reputation, praise or other prizes that are not in the form of material or money. The two incentives are a very important part of the reciprocal relationship between employees and agencies which in the future are expected to produce higher quality employee performance.

In addition to employee satisfaction, another thing that is no less important for the agency is motivation. According to Luthans (2014: 204) "motivation is a process that begins with a physiological or psychological definition that drives behavior or drives aimed at goals or incentives". Motivation is the spirit for each individual that underlies them to act and do something. People will not do something optimally if they do not have high motivation from within themselves to do this. This is in accordance with Robbins' statement that "motivation is a process that explains the intensity, direction and persistence of an individual to achieve his goals". Motivation greatly affects the success of an agency, especially in an effort to improve employee performance. Employee performance is defined as employee behavior towards work and aspects of work. According to Hasibuan (2010: 56), an increase in employee performance can be shown by an increase in work performance and an increase in employee work behavior (self-development, integrity, building trust, professionalism, teamwork and attendance). By providing the right work motivation for employees to work better, employees will have the enthusiasm to work so that the work assigned to employees can be completed more efficiently.

The Office of Investment and One Stop Integrated Services has the task of formulating and implementing policies in the investment sector as well as administering investment administration, licensing and non-licensing services in an integrated manner with the principles of coordination, integration, synchronization, simplification, security, certainty and transparency. In the last few months there have been several problems that have occurred at the Investment and One Stop Service Office. This will result in increased absenteeism and decreased job satisfaction of the employees themselves. An employee who is dissatisfied with his job can be motivated to work even better to improve himself. So with a high work motivation will be reflected in a sense of responsibility and passion for work that creates a desire to work and give the best for his work. The form of motivation can be seen based on the performance results that have been completed by this agency.

Table 1.1: Performance of the Investment Service and Integrated Services 2022

Strategic target	Program Goals	Target	Achievement
Fulfillment of Administrative Services	Office Administration Service Program	1 year	80%
Increasing the quality of civil servants	Apparatus Resource Capacity Building Program	1 year	90%
Licensing control	Licensing program	1 year	76%
Harmonization of licensing policies	Licensing Compatibility Program	1 year	66%

Source: Data processed by Dpmp . Service

Previous research has proven that intrinsic motivation has a significant effect on job satisfaction. This is proven through research conducted by Murti (2010) in his research explaining that the better the fulfillment of the needs of employees, the better the intrinsic motivation given to employees and in the end they get high job satisfaction as well. Employee satisfaction is the fulfillment of wants and needs through work activities. Needs are one of the important factors to motivate employees because as humans, they must have various primary and secondary needs. Employees will be motivated if their needs are met, with the fulfillment of needs, employee satisfaction will arise. This is one of the reasons why the author intends to study more deeply about the things that cause a decrease in performance in the company employees of the Medan City One Stop Integrated Investment and Licensing Service Office.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Satisfaction

Theoretically the notion of job satisfaction has been put forward by several expert. One of them is according to Sudaryo, Agus & Nunung (2018) job satisfaction is a pleasant or unpleasant feeling about work based on expectations with rewards provided by the agency. Meanwhile, another opinion about job satisfaction was also put forward by Hasibuan (2017) job satisfaction is a pleasant emotional attitude and loves his job. This attitude is reflected by work morale, discipline, and work performance. Job satisfaction is enjoyed at work, outside of work, and combination of inside and outside work. Job satisfaction at work is Job satisfaction enjoyed at work by obtaining praise for work, placement, treatment, equipment, and a good work environment. While job satisfaction outside of work is employee job satisfaction that is enjoyed outside of work with the amount of remuneration that will be received from the results of his work, so that he can buy his needs. Employees who prefer to enjoy their satisfaction outside of work are more concerned with remuneration than carrying out their duties.

Intrinsic Motivation

Motivation is needed because without motivation, employees are not encouraged to produce increased and good productivity. Motivation itself is very influential and plays an important role. According to Priyatama (2009) said intrinsic motivation is a value or a combination of enjoyment or pleasure in carrying out a task for a particular purpose, it can be said that intrinsic

motivation that functions as a reward is individual behavior in carrying out these activities, not external rewards. Suwatno (2011:175) states "intrinsic motivation is the motives that become active or function do not need to be stimulated from outside, because in every individual there is an urge to do something". according to Husaini Usman (2009:249) defines "intrinsic motivation is motivation that arises from within oneself".

Incentive

According to Mangkunegara (2011: 89) the definition of incentives is:as follows: "Incentive is a form of money given by the leader organization to employees so that they work with high motivationhigh achievement and achievement in achieving organizational goals as an acknowledgment of work performance and employee contributions to the organization." According to Panggabean (2010: 89) the definition of incentives is as follows: Incentives are rewards in the form of money given to those who can work beyond predetermined standards.

Hypothesis

Based on the problem formulation that has been stated above, the research hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H1 = Intrinsic Motivation Affects IncentivesAt the Office of the Investment and Licensing Service Office One Stop Integrated Medan City.

H2 = Intrinsic Motivation has an effect onEmployee Satisfaction At the Office of the Investment and Licensing Service Office One Stop Integrated Medan City.

H3 = Incentives affectEmployee Satisfaction At the Office of the Investment and Licensing Service Office One Stop Integrated Medan City.

H4 = Incentives mediate the effect of Intrinsic Motivation onEmployee Satisfaction At the Office of the Investment and Licensing Service Office One Stop Integrated Medan City.

METHOD APPROACH

Research Objects and Locations

This research was conducted at the Office of the One-Stop Integrated Licensing and Investment Service Office, Medan City.

Types of research

According to Sugiyono (2015:34), the types of data are divided into 2, namely qualitative and quantitative. This study uses the types of data in the form of qualitative and quantitative. Qualitative data according to Sugiyono (2015:22) is data in the form of words, schemes, and pictures. The qualitative data of this research are the names and addresses of the research objects. Quantitative data according to Sugiyono (2015:23) is data in the form of numbers or qualitative data that is numbered.

DATA COLLECTION TECHNIQUE

Questionnaires or questionnaires are a number of questions or written statements about factual data or opinions relating to the respondent, which are considered facts or truths that are known and need to be answered by the respondent (Suroyo Anwar, 2011:29). In this questionnaire, a closed question model will be used, namely questions that have been accompanied by previous alternative answers so that respondents can choose one of these alternative answers. According to Sugiyono (2015: 49) interviews are data collection techniques if researchers want to conduct a preliminary study to find problems that must be investigated, but also if researchers want to know things from respondents more deeply.

Data analysis method

Data analysis is a desire to group, make a sequence, manipulate and abbreviate data so that it is easy to read and understand. Can answer the problem in accordance with the research objectives and can test the hypothesis (Silaendan Widiyono, 2013:31).

DISCUSSION

Classical Assumption Test Equation 1

The tests of classical assumptions with the SPSS 25.00 program carried out in this study include:

Normality test

Normality test aims to test whether in the regression model, the confounding or residual variables have a normal distribution (Ghozali, 2016). Testing the normality of the data can be done by using a normal probability plot. Normality test using the graphical method can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 4.1 Normal P Plot

Data that is normally distributed will form a straight diagonal line and plotting residual data will be compared with a diagonal line, if the distribution of residual data is normal, the line that describes the actual data will follow the diagonal line (Ghozali, 2016).

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether from the regression model there is an inequality of variance from the residuals of one observation to another observation. A good regression model is one with homoscedasticity or no heteroscedasticity.

Table 4.1 Glejser Test Results

Model		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.710	1.497		.474	.639
	Motivation_Intrinsic_X	.036	.122	.056	.296	.769

a. Dependent Variable: Abs_RES

Source: Data processed from attachment 4 (2022)

Based on the above test, the significance value of Intrinsic Motivation (X) is greater than 0.05 (5%) which is 0.769, so there is no indication of heteroscedasticity.

Simple Linear Regression Test

Multiple linear regression testing explains the magnitude of the role of the Intrinsic Motivation variable (X) on the Incentive variable (Z). Data analysis in this study used multiple linear regression analysis using SPSS 25.0 for windows. The analysis of each variable is described in the following description:

Table 4.2 Simple Linear Regression Results

Model		Coefficients ^a						
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	9,648	2,580		3.739	.001		
	Motivation_Intrinsic_X	.218	.211	.192	1.033	.310	1,000	1,000

a. Dependent Variable: Incentive_Z

Source: Data processed from attachment 4 (2022)

Based on these results, the multiple linear regression equation has the following formulation: $Z = a + b X +$, so that the equation is obtained: $Z = 9,648 + 0,218 X +$

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination is used to see how much the independent variable contributes to the dependent variable. The greater the value of the coefficient of determination, the better the ability of the independent variable to explain the dependent variable. If the determination

(R2) is getting bigger (closer to 1), it can be said that the influence of the variable Intrinsic Motivation (X) is big against Incentive variable (Z).

Table 4.3 Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.192a	.037	.122	1.464	2,084
a. Predictors: (Constant), Motivation_X					
b. Dependent Variable: Incentive_Y1					

Source: Data processed from attachment 4 (2022)

Based on table 4.3, it can be seen that the adjusted R square value is 0.122 or 12.2%. This shows if variable Intrinsic Motivation (X) can explain the Incentive variable (Z) by 12.2%, the remaining 87.8% (100% - 12.2%) is explained by other variables outside this research model.

Classical Assumption Test Equation 2

The tests of classical assumptions with the SPSS 25.00 program carried out in this study include:

Normality test

Normality test aims to test whether in the regression model, the confounding or residual variables have a normal distribution (Ghozali, 2016). Testing the normality of the data can be done by using a normal probability plot. Normality test using the graphical method can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 4.2 Normal P Plot

Data that is normally distributed will form a straight diagonal line and plotting residual data will be compared with a diagonal line, if the distribution of residual data is normal, the line that describes the actual data will follow the diagonal line (Ghozali, 2016).

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test aims to determine whether there is a correlation between the independent variables in the regression model. The multicollinearity test in this study is seen from the tolerance value or variance inflation factor (VIF).

Table 4.4 Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients ^a							
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	7329	4.450		1,647	.111		
Motivation_Intrinsic_X	1.003	.303	.545	3.313	.003	.963	1.038
Incentive_Z	-.013	.266	-.008	-.050	.960	.963	1.038

a. Dependent Variable: Job_Satisfaction_Y

Source: Data processed from attachment 4 (2022)

The tolerance value of Motivation (X) is 0.963, Incentive (Z) is 0.963, all of which are greater than 0.10 while the VIF value of Intrinsic Motivation (X) is 1.038 and Incentive (Z) is 1.038, all of which are less than 10. Based on the calculation results above, it can be seen that the tolerance value of all independent variables is greater than 0.10 and the VIF value of all independent variables is also smaller than 5 so that there is no correlation symptom in the independent variables. So it can be concluded that there is no symptom of multicollinearity between independent variables in the regression model.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether from the regression model there is an inequality of variance from the residuals of one observation to another observation. A good regression model is one with homoscedasticity or no heteroscedasticity.

Table 4.5. Glejser Test Results

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.887	2,397		1,204	.239
Motivation_Intrinsic_X	.098	.163	.114	.602	.552
Incentive_Z	-.200	.143	-.264	-1,395	.175

a. Dependent Variable: Abs_RES

Source: Data processed from attachment 4 (2022)

Based on the above test, the significance value of Intrinsic Motivation (X) is greater than 0.05 (5%) which is 0.552, Incentive (Z) is greater than 0.05 (5%) which is 0.175, so there is no indication of heteroscedasticity.

Multiple Linear Regression Test

Multiple linear regression testing explains the magnitude of the role of Intrinsic Motivation (X) and Incentives (Z) on Job Satisfaction (Y). Data analysis in this study used multiple linear regression analysis using SPSS 25.0 for windows.

Table 4.6 Multiple Linear Regression Results

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	7329	4.450		1,647	.111		
	Motivation_Intrinsic_X	1.003	.303	.545	3.313	.003	.963	1.038
	Incentive_Z	-.013	.266	-.008	-.050	.960	.963	1.038

a. Dependent Variable: Job_Satisfaction_Y

Source: Data processed from attachment 4 (2022)

Based on these results, the multiple linear regression equation has the following formulation: $Y = a + b_1X + b_2Z$, so that the equation is obtained: $Y = 7.329 + 1.003 X + -0.013 Z$

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination is used to see how much the independent variable contributes to the dependent variable. The greater the value of the coefficient of determination, the better the ability of the independent variable to explain the dependent variable. If the determination (R²) is getting bigger (closer to 1), it can be said that the influence of the variable X is large on Incentive(Z).

Table 4.7 Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.544a	.296	.243	2,062	1.376

a. Predictors: (Constant), Incentive_Z, Motivation_X
b. Dependent Variable: Job_Satisfaction_Y

Source: Data processed from attachment 4 (2022)

Based on table 4.7, it can be seen that the adjusted R square value is 0.243 or 24.3%. This shows that incentives (Z) and intrinsic motivation (X) can explain job satisfaction (Y) by 24.3%, the remaining 75.7% (100% - 24.3%) is explained by other variables outside the research model. this.

Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis testing is a decision-making method based on data analysis, both from controlled experiments, and from observations.

t test (Partial)

The t statistic test is also known as the individual significance test. This test shows how far the influence of the independent variable partially on the dependent variable.

Table 4.8 Partial Test (t) Equation 1

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	9,648	2,580		3.739	.001		
	Motivation_Intrinsic_X	.218	.211	.192	1.033	.310	1,000	1,000

a. Dependent Variable: Incentive_Z

Source: Data processed from attachment 4 (2022)

a. Hypothesis Testing the effect of Intrinsic Motivation variable (X) on Incentive variable (Z).

Obtained tcount value of 1.033 With = 5%, ttable (5%; nk = 28) obtained ttable value of 1.701 From the description it can be seen that tcount (1.033) < ttable (1.701), as well as the significance value of 0.00 > 0.05, it can be concluded that the first hypothesis is rejected, meaning that the variable MotivationIntrinsic (X) has no positive and significant effectto Incentives (Z).

Table 4.9 Partial Test (t) of Equation 2

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	7329	4.450		1,647	.111		
	Motivation_Intrinsic_X	1.003	.303	.545	3.313	.003	.963	1.038
	Incentive_Z	-.013	.266	-.008	-.050	.960	.963	1.038

a. Dependent Variable: Job_Satisfaction_Y

Source: Data processed from attachment 4 (2022)

a) Hypothesis Testing the Effect of Intrinsic Motivation(X)on Job Satisfaction (Y)

Obtained a tcount value of 3.313 With = 5%, ttable (5%; nk = 28) obtained a ttable value of 1.701. From this description it can be seen that tcount (3.313) > ttable (1.701), and the significance value is 0.00 < 0 0.05, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis is accepted,

meaning that Motivation Intrinsic (X) has a positive and significant effect on Employee Satisfaction (Y).

b) Hypothesis Testing the Effect of Incentives (Z) on Job Satisfaction (Y)

Obtained t count value of -0.050 With = 5%, t table (5%; nk = 28) obtained t table value of 1.701 From the description it can be seen that t count (-0.050) < t table (1.701), and the significance value is 0.00 > 0.05, it can be concluded that the third hypothesis is rejected, meaning that Incentive (Z) no effect positive and significant on Job Satisfaction (Y).

Path Analysis

In order to prove that whether a variable is capable of being a variable that mediates the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable, the direct and indirect effects of the independent variable on the dependent variable will be calculated. If the indirect effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable through the intervening variable is greater than the direct effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable, then that variable can be a variable that mediates between the independent variable and the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2016). To carry out calculations directly and indirectly, it is carried out from the following standardized coefficients of regression equations I and II:

Table 4.10 Value of Standardized Coefficients Equation I

Coefficients a			
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients
	B	Std. Error	Beta
(Constant)	9,648	2,580	
Motivation_Intrinsic_X	.218	.211	.192

a. Dependent Variable: Incentive_Z

Table 4.11 Value of Standardized Coefficients Equation II

Coefficients a			
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients
	B	Std. Error	Beta
1 (Constant)	7329	4.450	
Motivation_Intrinsic_X	1.003	.303	.545
Incentive_Z	-.013	.266	-.008

a. Dependent Variable: Job_Satisfaction_Y

Furthermore, the standardized coefficients beta values will be included in the path analysis image as follows:

Figure 4.3 Path Analysis

A Path analysis shows the direct effect of variable X on variable Y of 0.545. While the indirect effect through variable Z is $0.192 \times 0.008 = 0.0153$ from the calculation results obtained, it shows the direct effect through variable X is greater than the indirect effect on variable Y. These results can be seen in the following table:

Table 4.12 Direct and Indirect Relationships

No	Variable	Direct	Indirect	Total	Criteria	Conclusion
1	Intrinsic Motivation (X)	0.545	0.192	-	Significant	As Independent Variable
2	Incentive (Z)	0.008	-	0.015	Significant No Positive	No As an Intervening Variable

Source: Data processed from attachment 4 (2022)

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion in the previous chapter, it can be concluded as follows:

1. It can be seen that $t_{count} (1.033) < t_{table} (1.701)$, as well as the significance value of $0.00 > 0.05$, it can be concluded that the first hypothesis is rejected, meaning that the motivation variable Intrinsic (X) has no positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction (Z).
2. It can be seen that $t_{count} (3.313) > t_{table} (1.701)$, and the significance value is $0.00 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis is accepted, meaning that Motivation Intrinsic (X) has a significant effect on Job Satisfaction (Y).
3. It can be seen that $t_{count} (-0.050) < t_{table} (1.701)$, and the significance value is $0.00 > 0.05$, it can be concluded that the third hypothesis is rejected, meaning that Incentive (Z) no effect positive and significant on Job Satisfaction (Y).
4. Path analysis shows that the direct effect of variable X on variable Y is 0.545. While the indirect effect through the Z variable is $0.192 \times 0.008 = 0.0153$ from the calculation results obtained, it shows that the indirect effect through the Z variable is smaller than the direct effect on the Y variable.

SUGGESTION

Suggestions that can be given, based on the results of the analysis, discussion and conclusions are that agencies should pay attention to providing intrinsic motivation to their employees, especially in providing opportunities to achieve work performance so as to encourage employee morale at work. Agencies should also give trust to employees so as to encourage employees to complete work on time, thus employees are expected to be able to survive and be loyal to the agency. Agencies should also give various tasks to employees to encourage employees to develop more. Agencies should pay attention to the job satisfaction of their employees. Increasing job satisfaction for employees can be done by providing wages in accordance with the workload and responsibilities of employees in the agency.

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